

Awareness of Pakistani Medical Students and Interns about COVID 2019

Malghalara Naeem¹, Alishba Khan², Muhammad Mohsin Ali³, Qudsia anwar⁴, Muhammad Zeeshan Sarwar⁵, Sarmad Zahoor⁶

Abstract

Objective: The objective of this study was to determine knowledge and awareness among medical students and interns regarding COVID-19.

Materials and Methods: An observational cross-sectional survey with 217 participants was carried out among medical students and interns of King Edward Medical University, and Mayo Hospital Lahore from March to May 2020.

Results: Among participants, 62.2% were female, with 134 (61.8%) medical students and 83 (38.2%) medical interns. Social media was the most common source (39.9%) of information regarding COVID-19. Medical students and interns alike had good knowledge regarding the pandemic status of COVID-19 (91.7%); the relationship of COVID-19 with other coronaviruses; presence of asymptomatic carriers (84.3%); crude mortality rate (77.4%); and preventive measures (98.6%). However, knowledge about virus structure, genus, transmission, epidemiological characteristics, diagnosis, prevention and treatment was found to be inadequate among both interns and students.

Conclusion: There is poor over all knowledge among medical students and interns regarding COVID-19, especially during a pandemic. Steps must be taken to improve knowledge by introducing changes in curriculum related to emerging diseases, and by active participation of medical students in learning and dissemination of information on COVID-19.

Keywords: COVID-19, Medical students, Internship and residency, Awareness, Curriculum.

Introduction

The novel corona virus disease (COVID-19), with its first case reported in Wuhan, China in December 2019,¹ has now become a raging pandemic affecting more than 21 million people globally; and as of 16th August 2020, has reached a death toll greater than 0.7 million people.² It has henceforth been declared a public health emergency by US Centers for Disease Control (CDC).³ This strain of coronavirus is a betacoronavirus, consisting of a

positive sense single stranded RNA and has been largely isolated from bats. This outbreak serves as clear evidence of its zoonotic as well as human to human transmission⁴

Previously, epidemics due to other coronavirus diseases have been reported by the WHO. A SARS-CoV epidemic occurred in China in 2002, and MERS-CoV epidemic occurred in Saudi Arabia in 2012.⁵ There is a great need for awareness about COVID-19 as previous studies conducted during other epidemics have shown that adherence to precautionary measures is influenced by the insight of the population regarding the problem.^{6,7}

Healthcare professionals and medical students in their clinical years are at a risk of both contracting the virus and spreading it to more susceptible individuals (people with comorbidities), and are also responsible for the initial recognition and detection of signs and symptoms in patients.⁸ Since they also serve as health advocates in the society, it is imperative for them to be

- | | |
|----------------------------|---------------------------|
| 1. Malghalara Naeem | 2. Alishba Khan |
| 3. Muhammad Mohsin Ali | 4. Muhammad Abbas Khokhar |
| 5. Muhammad Zeeshan Sarwar | 6. Sarmad Zahoor |
- 1-3: Department of Internal Medicine & Allied Specialties, KEMU, Mayo Hospital Lahore.
4: Head, Department of Oncology and Radiotherapy, MHL
5: Department of General Surgery, Mayo Hospital Lahore
6: Department of Internal Medicine, Mayo Hospital Lahore.

Correspondence

Muhammad Mohsin
House Officer, Department of Internal Medicine & Allied Specialties, King Edward Medical University, Mayo Hospital Lahore,
mohsinali@kemu.edu.pk

Submission Date:	19-08-2020
1st Revision Date:	25-08-2020
Acceptance Date:	12-09-2020

knowledgeable regarding the transmissibility, diagnostic tests, treatment and prevention of the disease.

The aim of this study is to assess awareness among medical students and interns regarding structure, transmission, infectivity, diagnosis and treatment of COVID 19. This will help us to identify gaps in knowledge and awareness, and to propose methods by which these can be improved for better provision of healthcare as well as better dissemination of relevant knowledge to the COVID-19 affected populace.

Methods

An observational cross-sectional study was carried out among clinical year medical students (3rd year to final year) of King Edward Medical University and medical interns working in general surgery, internal medicine and allied specialty departments of Mayo hospital, Lahore. Non-probability sampling was carried out: a random set of students and interns, identified through university and hospital records, were sent an online survey. Acceptance of online invite was taken as voluntary participation in the study. Pre-clinical medical students, students from allied health departments, residents and medical officers were excluded from the study.

Data was collected using a 19 item self-designed questionnaire based on objective type, multiple choice short questions, which tested the knowledge of medical students and interns across three domains: their knowledge of virology and disease transmission pattern; their awareness of epidemiological characteristics; and their knowledge regarding diagnosis, preventive measures and treatment. Questions were drafted from previous literature regarding awareness of medical students about MERS and influenza during pandemics⁹⁻¹¹ and were evaluated by experts in internal medicine and infectious diseases prior to dissemination.

Statistics

Data was analyzed using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0. Qualitative statistics such as gender, prior knowledge, sources of information, and responses to the questions were determined as frequency and percentages. For descriptive variables such as age and total score across

each domain tested, mean and standard deviation were calculated. Independent t-test was used to determine association of gender, status as medical student or intern, and prior knowledge with scoring in each domain, whereas one way ANOVA was used to determine association of year of medical education, department of intern, and source of information with total score in each domain, with P value <0.05 being considered significant.

Results

Out of 450 participants who were invited to partake in the survey, a total of 217 participants responded, including 37.8% (n=82) males and 62.2% (135) females. Mean age of the participants was 22.99 ± 1.73. Eighty three (38.2%) medical interns and 134 (61.8%) medical students participated. The various demographic details of the participants are outlined in table 1.

A 19 item questionnaire was used to assess awareness among medical students and interns. The answers of the respondents are summarized in table 2.

Independent t-test was used to determine the correlation between score in each domain with gender, prior knowledge, and student/intern status. The mean score of knowledge regarding virology was 4.14±1.48 out of total 8; mean score in epidemiology was 3.46±1.07 out of total of 6; whereas mean score in prevention and management was 3.05±0.75 out of total 4. No significant association of gender with total score in any of three domains was found by independent t-test (P>0.05). Interns (4.39±1.48) had significantly higher knowledge of virology compared to medical students (3.98±1.47; however, no significant differences in knowledge were observed in the other two domains. Prior knowledge of COVID-19 (present = 4.45±1.44; absent=3.89±1.48) was also significantly associated with better knowledge of virology; no corresponding association was recorded with knowledge of epidemiology or disease prevention and management. Table 3 summarizes the results of significant correlations on independent samples t-test.

Tables 4 and 5 shows the results of one-way ANOVA with post-hoc Tukey test for knowledge across domains with year of medical education. No significant associations were determined between know-

Table 1: Demographics of Study Participants

Variable	Category	Frequency
Gender	Male	82 (37.7%)
	Female	135 (62.2%)
Student or Intern	Medical Students	134 (61.8%)
	Medical Interns	83 (38.2%)
Academic Year for Medical Students	3 rd year	38 (28.3%)
	4 th year	33 (24.6%)
	5 th year	63 (47.0%)
Department of Internship	General Surgery	14 (16.8%)
	Allied Surgery	19 (22.8%)
	General Medicine	24 (28.9%)
	Allied Medicine	26 (31.3%)
Prior knowledge of COVID-19 before the outbreak in Pakistan	Yes	97 (44.7%)
	No	120 (55.3%)
Source of information regarding COVID-19	Lecture, Conference or Seminar in Medical College	49 (15.4%)
	Social Media	127 (39.9%)
	Print Media	28 (8.8%)
	Television	42 (13.2%)
	Mosque	3 (0.9%)
	Local Community	19 (5.9%)
	Government Press Release (from Ministry of Health)	11 (3.5%)
	Never heard of it before	39 (12.3%)

ledge and source of information or department of medical interns.

Discussion

Currently the COVID-19 pandemic is rampant across the globe. In light of the recent circumstances, it became crucial to carry out a study to assess the awareness of our medical students and interns, with regards to the structure, transmission, infectivity, diagnosis and treatment of COVID-19. No such study had been carried out until now, thus further highlighting its need.

Our study revealed social media as the most popular source of information (40%). The role of social media in disseminating healthcare information is documented in literature; sometimes, it might even be the only channel of pursuing and sharing health information.¹² Healthcare information on social media is a two-edged sword; while it can benefit a large amount of the population, wrong information or communicative gap can potentially cause harm as well.¹³ Research from the Ebola outbreak in Africa shows that social media users can consciously choose to engage with particular healthcare information during

a pandemic, and their online behavior can determine the degree of information amplification.¹⁴

Knowledge scores regarding virology were found to

Table 2: Responses to Questionnaire on Awareness Among Medical Students and Interns

Question	Correct Response n(%)
Section 1: Knowledge of Virology	
In your opinion n -COVID -19 stands for?	90 (41.5%)
COVID-19 is caused by which virus?	116 (53.5%)
Have you heard of any other Corona virus diseases before?	112 (51.6%)
	84 (38.7%)
	21 (9.7%)
In your opinion, is COVID -19 related to SARS and MERS?	173 (79.7%)
What is the structure of virus causing COVID -19?	166 (76.5)
To what genus does the virus causing COVID -19 belong to?	35 (16.1%)
The median incubation period of this virus is:	33 (15.2%)
The primary host for the new corona virus is:	151 (69.6%)
The virus responsible for COVID -19 can be transmitted by:	136 (62.7%)
Section 2: Knowledge of Epidemiology	
The WHO has declared COVID -19 as which of the following?	199 (91.7%)
Can a person be infected with COVID -19 and not have any symptoms?	183 (84.3%)
The fraction of moderate to severe COVID-19 infections requiring hospitalization is:	63 (29.0%)
The fraction of severe COVID -19 infections requiring artificial ventilation is:	62 (28.6%)
The crude mortality ratio of COVID-19 is:	168 (77.4%)
What is the estimated number of COVID-19 infected patients globally in February 2020?	77 (35.5%)
Section 3: Knowledge of Prevention and Management	
Prevention of spread of COVID -19 is by?	214 (98.6%)
Is there an available vaccine for COVID-19?	204 (94.0%)
What is the confirmatory test for COVID-19?	143 (65.9%)
Treatment of COVID -19 is?	106 (48.8%)

be low among the participants (mean 4.14 out of 8). This points towards the general lack of knowledge among students and interns in basic sciences. In a

Table 3: Correlations Knowledge of Virology on Independent T-test

Correlation between Variables	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				
	F	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Total Score in Virology (Students vs Interns)	0.845	-1.998	215	.047	-0.412	-0.819	-0.005
Total Score in Virology (No prior knowledge vs prior knowledge)	0.020	2.809	215	0.005	0.561	0.167	0.956

Table 4: ANOVA Showing Correlation Between Knowledge Across Domains with Year of Medical Education

Correlations		df	F	Sig.
Total Score in Epidemiology	Between Groups	3	5.825	.001
	Within Groups	213		
Total Score in Prevention and Management	Between Groups	3	7.699	.000
	Within Groups	213		
Total Score in Virology	Between Groups	3	4.284	.006
	Within Groups	213		

study carried out on healthcare professionals regarding MERS-CoV infection in Madina in 2019, similar results were reported regarding lack of knowledge in virology, with only 44.5% of the participants knowing that MERS-CoV was an RNA virus.¹⁵ A study from Saudi Arabia showed how inadequate history taking skills, and poor recognition of signs and symptoms of MERS-CoV infection contribute to mismanagement and misdiagnosis of the patients⁽¹⁶⁾. In a study assessing knowledge of Saudi medical students regarding MERS-CoV, 86% of students were unaware of its structure as a betacoronavirus, while 80% were unaware of the structure of single stranded RNA viruses.⁹ A knowledge, attitude and practice (KAP) study from Saudi Arabia identified that about 67.6% of the participants had poor knowledge and 91.8% had a negative attitude with regards to MERS-CoV infection.¹⁷

Students and interns equally did not have sound knowledge regarding the epidemiology of COVID-19. Around 71% of our participants had no knowledge of the fractional percentage of patients that might require hospitalization and assisted ventilation. This is contrasting to a study conducted in Saudi Arabia during the outbreak of MERS, where medical students' knowledge regarding the transmission (97.1%), and treatment options (61%) for MERS showed far better results.⁹ Similarly, poor results regarding knowledge, awareness and practice regarding swine flu during an epidemic were reported from Gujrat, India, in which only 16% were aware of diagnosis using a throat swab and 30% respondents had correct information about management guidelines for swine flu.¹¹ An earlier study conducted to assess the knowledge of medical students regarding influenza pandemic at the University of Alberta also showed significant gaps regarding knowledge of transmission, prevention and treatment among medical students.¹⁰

Apart from this, the comprehension of the treatment options available was limited, with more than half of participants (51.2%) failing to understand that fluids and supportive care are the mainstay of treatment of viral infections like COVID-19. The role of antivirals in treating COVID-19 is yet to be established, and so far no conclusive evidence is available in this regard.¹⁸

Table 5: Post-hoc Tukey Test Showing Correlation between Various Years of Medical Education with Score Across Domains

Dependent Variable	(I) Academic Year	(J) Academic Year	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Total Score in Epidemiology	3rd Year	5th Year	.804*	.001	.2529	1.3561
Total Score in Prevention and Management	3rd Year	4th Year	-.598*	.004	-1.0458	-.1520
		5th Year	-.669*	.000	-1.0554	-.2838
Total Score in Virology	3rd Year	5th Year	.811*	.036	.0374	1.5858

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Medical students and interns, being health advisory as well as advocates, play an integral part in our community. They should remain up to date with regards to both the pathological and the clinical features of COVID-19. The shortcomings we witnessed in the basic knowledge of our medical students can be overcome by devising a curriculum that covers the pathological, epidemiological and clinical aspects of COVID-19.¹⁹To deal with health emergencies such as the COVID-19 pandemic, medical students should undertake courses in tropical medicine, field epidemiology, and infectious diseases as part of their medical curriculum.²⁰ More immediate solutions could be online education through short certificate courses for medical students and simulation based learning for real world situations.

This study has certain strengths and limitations. To our knowledge, it is the first study of its kind reporting awareness of COVID-19 among medical students and interns in Pakistan. It highlights the lack of knowledge of students and interns about an ongoing pandemic, and suggests approaches to address areas where students are lacking. It also shows how factors such as prior knowledge of COVID-19 and sources of information can affect awareness among medical students in different years of medical education.

Limitations of the study include its cross-sectional design; and the lack of a comparable cohort from other medical institutes and private sector hospitals.

Conclusion

Our study showed that both medical students and interns have poor knowledge regarding virology, transmission and epidemiology, and treatment of COVID-19 during a pandemic. While the knowledge of interns and final year medical students was significantly better regarding basic virology, it was still inadequate across all three domains tested in our study. Participants had a good knowledge regarding preventive measures, which is an important aspect of practice in the setting of COVID-19 pandemic. Since the COVID-19 pandemic is an evolving situation, our study could serve as a baseline study for future comparisons of knowledge of healthcare professionals and medical students both during this pandemic and future outbreaks, and can help design policies to improve continuing medical education and clinical practice.

Disclaimer: None

Conflict of Interest: None

Funding Sources: None

Author's Contribution:

MN, AK: Data Collection and analysis.

MMA: Writeup & lead article.

QAD: Data analysis and proof reading.

MZS: Concept and writeup.

SZ: Concept and analysis, proof reading.

Conflict of Interest: None

References

1. Lai C-C, Shih T-P, Ko W-C, Tang H-J, Hsueh P-R. Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) and corona virus disease-2019 (COVID-19): the epidemic and the challenges. *Int J Antimicrob Agents*. 2020;105924.
2. WHO. Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Situation Report – 209: WHO; 2020 [cited 2020 10th April]. Available from: https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/coronaviruse/situation-reports/20200816-covid-19-sitrep-209.pdf?sfvrsn=5dde1ca2_2
3. Qarawi ATA, Ng SJ, Gad A, Mai LN, AL-Ahdal TMA, Sharma A, et al. Awareness and Preparedness of Hospital Staff against Novel Coronavirus (COVID-2019): A Global Survey-Study Protocol. *SSRN*. 2020.
4. Paules CI, Marston HD, Fauci AS. Coronavirus infections—more than just the common cold. *JAMA*. 2020;323(8):707-8.
5. Lu R, Zhao X, Li J, Niu P, Yang B, Wu H, et al. Genomic characterisation and epidemiology of 2019 novel coronavirus: implications for virus origins and receptor binding. *Lancet*. 2020;395(10224):565-74.
6. Ajilore K, Atakiti I, Onyenakeya K. College students' knowledge, attitudes and adherence to public service announcements on Ebola in Nigeria: Suggestions for improving future Ebola prevention education programmes. *Health Education Journal*. 2017;76(6):648-60.
7. Tachfouti N, Slama K, Berraho M, Nejjari C. The impact of knowledge and attitudes on adherence to tuberculosis treatment: a case-control study in a Moroccan region. *Pan African Medical Journal*. 2012;12(1).
8. Team NCPERE. The epidemiological characteristics of an outbreak of 2019 novel coronavirus diseases (COVID-19) in China. *ZHONGHUA LIUXING-BINGXUE ZAZHI* 2020;41(2):145.

9. Al-Mohrej A, Agha S. Are Saudi medical students aware of middle east respiratory syndrome coronavirus during an outbreak? *Journal of infection and public health*. 2017;10(4):388-95.
10. Herman B, Rosychuk RJ, Bailey T, Lake R, Yonge O, Marrie TJ. Medical students and pandemic influenza. *EID*. 2007;13(11):1781.
11. Trivedi B, Rana D, Trivedi R, Malhotra S. Lack of Knowledge, Awareness among Gujarati Medical Undergraduates for Swine Flu Epidemic: A Boon to the Disease. *National Journal of Integrated Research in Medicine*. 2017;8(5).
12. Zhou Z, Bai R. Roles of Social Media in Disseminating Health Information: An Exploratory Study in China. In: D. Vogel XG, C. Barry, M. Lang, H. Linger, & C. Schneider editor. *Information Systems Development: Transforming Healthcare through Information Systems (ISD2015 Proceedings)*. Hong Kong: SAR: Department of Information Systems.; 2015.
13. Szomszor M, Kostkova P, St Louis C, editors. *Twitter informatics: tracking and understanding public reaction during the 2009 swine flu pandemic*. 2011 IEEE/WIC/ACM International Conferences on Web Intelligence and Intelligent Agent Technology; 2011: IEEE.
14. Strekalova YA. Health risk information engagement and amplification on social media: News about an emerging pandemic on Facebook. *Health Educ Behav*. 2017;44(2):332-9.
15. Alanzi ME, Albalawi MAH, Kabrah S, Aljehani YT, Okashah AM, Aljohani ZDE, et al. Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAPs) of Healthcare Workers towards MERS-CoV Infection at PHCs in Madinah, KSA during Hajj 1440, 2019. *American Journal of Microbiological Research*. 2019;7(4):122-9.
16. Gaffar BO, El Tantawi M, Al-Ansari AA, AlAgl AS, Farooqi FA, Almas KM. Knowledge and practices of dentists regarding MERS-CoV. *Saudi Med J*. 2019;40(7):714-20.
17. Nour MO, Babilghith AO, Natto HA, Al-Amin FO, Alawneh SM. Knowledge, attitude and practices of healthcare providers towards MERS-CoV infection at Makkah hospitals, KSA. *Int Res J Med Med Sci*. 2015;3(4):103-12.
18. Singhal T. A Review of Coronavirus Disease-2019 (COVID-19). *The Indian Journal of Pediatrics*. 2020:1-6.
19. Buckley MRF. Harvard Medical School students mobilize 2020 [cited 2020 March 25]. Available from: <https://news.harvard.edu/gazette/story/2020/03/harvard-m-d-students-form-covid-19-rapid-response-teams/>.
20. Guerrier G, D'Ortenzio E. Teaching anthropology to medical students. *Lancet*. 2015;385(9968):603.